

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Vocational School English Analysis Class (IKN-Science Fisheries)

Object;

Muthia Khairunnisa Analysis For *nilai moral dan nilai budaya pada film 5 elang*

Background and Analysis

5 Eagles movie is a production film original from Indonesia which was released on August 25, 2011. This film carries the theme of the family with the comedy-drama concept of children. this movie was directed by Rudi Soedjarwo and starred by Iqbaal Ramadhan, Teuku Rizky, Christoffer Nelwan, and Monica Sayangbati. Tell a student of an elementary school named Baron who came from Jakarta city but he should follow life her parents move to Balikpapan because of something necessity. The arrival of the 5 eagles movie society is highly appreciated well by the community. First, this movie reminds adults to reminisce about their childhood moments following training scouting. Second, this movie takes background places outside Jakarta, hal this includes Indonesian film that takes background non-Jakarta and non- Java representation. Third, this film is very suitable for children because many learn from it. To know moral values and values culture in the film 5 eagles, the writer uses the method descriptive with an approach qualitative. This research was conducted so that people know the moral values and cultural values in the film 5 eagles.

Based on the discussion study one could conclude that the movie 5 eagle Rudi Soedjarwo 's work is very educational, especially for teachers to children about how Upgrade courage, independence, honesty, and a sense of responsibility in answer to fellow. There is little similarity Between moral values and values culture. Both of them of course should apply in life every day, like how good communication with the group and always guard solidarity within the group (Fortes M & Evans-Pritchard, 2015).

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Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Questions:

- 1) Is it Available data or information to answer it,
Answer: Yes, data is available to answer the research problem
- 2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,
Answer: yes the data is obtained from sources of scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests. but rather using observation and documentation
- 3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts)
Answer: yes this paper meets the requirements of originality because it was made with my own idea and has been checked
- 4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science
Answer: yes my paper also makes a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science
- 5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening
Answer: Yes, I took the issue of friendship
- 6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and
Answer: no, this research only uses observation and documentation techniques by watching movies
- 7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.
Answer: no, this research was conducted for study purposes and not according to the author's interest
- 8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred
Answer : Just looking at something that is common in the environment seeing friendship
- 9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?
Answer: In the development of science, especially research and research is a field that must continue to be developed. the reason is that research here is a means to develop existing knowledge into new findings that can be useful for people's lives.

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